

Luminescent properties of Tb³⁺- doped P₂O₅ - Bi₂O₃ - SrF₂ - Na₂CO₃ glasses for green laser applications

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Abstract: A series of glass with suitable chemical compositions (60-x) P₂O₅ + 20 Bi₂O₃ + 10 SrF₂ + 10 Na₂CO₃ + xTb₄O₇ (x = 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0% by mole) were prepared by using the melt quenching technique. The X-ray diffraction technique was used to confirm the glass phase structure. The glass matrix's distinct functional groups and distinctive bonding vibrations are revealed by the structural study employing the FTIR technique. The EDAX spectrum was used to examine the elements found in the manufactured glass sample. Photoluminescence (PL) properties of the samples have been examined by excitation, emission and decay patterns. The emission studies revealed a significant green emission at 542 nm, which is associated with the Tb³⁺ ion's ⁵D₄→⁷F₅ transition. Measurements of the decay curves for the ⁵D₄ level of the Tb³⁺ ion revealed that they were single exponential in character, independent of the dopant concentration. The CIE chromaticity coordinates were revealed that the green emission was predominant in Tb³⁺- doped phosphate glasses.

Keywords: Tb³⁺ ion phosphate glasses, XRD, FTIR, Absorption spectra and Decay analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, visible fiber lasers, particularly those with green wavelengths have drawn interest for use in optical data storage, medical treatment, and visible light communication technologies [1]. In the past decades, through up-conversion luminescence methods, Er³⁺-doped phosphate glass fibers have been investigated for the creation of green fiber lasers upon either 800 or 980 nm laser diodes (LDs) [2]. It is generally known that non-radiative relaxation processes cause up-conversion processes to lose more energy; nonetheless, in order to obtain the laser output, a high pump power is needed. Considering the aforementioned facts and significance, it has been essential to see the alternative process to get the visible laser output with high quantum efficiency. Tb³⁺-activated phosphate glasses have shown promise as gain media in the green area at 542 nm because the Tb³⁺ ion's ⁵D₄→⁷F₅ transition offers a four-level laser system with a lower threshold pump power than Er³⁺ ions [3–7]. Furthermore, Tb³⁺ is a potential

ion for green laser applications because experimental branching ratios of the 542 nm band are typically greater than 50%. First documented in 1967, the green laser operation relied on the $^5D_4 \rightarrow ^7F_5$ transition of Tb^{3+} [8,9]. Additionally, watt-level GaN - related LDs from the ultraviolet to blue wavelength range have become commercially available, which accelerates the development of visible fiber lasers [10-11].

Terbium is a lanthanide, belonging to the rare-earth elements (REE) group. REE include lanthanum and the f-block elements, cerium through lutetium. Due to their similar ionic radii to the lighter f-block elements, scandium and yttrium are also included in this group. One significant characteristic of lanthanides is their ability to function as light-emitting activators in a variety of matrices. Due to the $^5D_4 \rightarrow ^7F_j$ ($j=0\dots6$) transition, the photoluminescence spectra of Tb^{3+} ions exhibit rather high emission in the visible and ultraviolet areas. In most of the Tb^{3+} doped phosphate glasses, the emission spectrum consists of four main emission bands centered at 620 nm (red), 582 nm (yellow), 542 nm (green) and the other in the high energy region centered at 440 nm (blue) [12,13]. Using measurements of optical absorption, photoluminescence, and decay, the spectroscopic characteristics of various concentrations of terbium-doped phosphate glasses have been examined in this chapter.

The phosphate glasses are one of the best materials for RE^{3+} ion doping due to its excellent properties. Due to their strong nonlinearity, high-concentration phosphate glasses with a high Bi_2O_3 content have found extensive use in optical applications. The SrF_2 compounds exhibit smaller spectral dispersion, a lower phonon energy, and a broad transparency range of 0.15 to 11 μm . Furthermore, SrF_2 can decrease the thermal performance of glass while increasing its clarity. The optical characteristics of phosphate glasses doped with strontium fluoride and bismuth oxide haven't, however, been thoroughly investigated. In light of these considerations, the main goal of this study is to develop a novel class of phosphate glasses (PBNSTb) doped with varying concentrations of Tb^{3+} ion were investigated through absorption, emission, excitation and decay measurements to assess their potentiality as a gain media at 542 nm. The concentration quenching effect on photoluminescence decay curves were examined.

2. EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

2.1. Sample preparation

The melt quenching technique was used to add terbium ions to phosphate glasses in different quantities. Glass is used in the following ways in the present work; ($x = 0.1, 0.5, 1.0,$

1.5, and 2.0% by mole) $(60-x) \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 + 20 \text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3 + 10 \text{SrF}_2 + 10 \text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 + x \text{Tb}_2\text{O}_3$. It is recommended that an alumina crucible with the composition inside should have a stoichiometric ratio of approximately 20 g. The composition needs to be heated to 1100°C in an electric furnace for 90 minutes in order to melt it uniformly. On the brass plate, this uniform slurry is rapidly poured and placed (preheated). The use of a second brass plate allows the melt to be compacted quickly and to be given thickness. The residual heat stress on the glass samples will be lessened. These produced samples were annealed at 400°C degrees for 10 h. To get the desired effects, the produced glass samples were then carefully polished. The manufactured samples were labeled as PBNSTb01 PBNSTb05 PBNSTb10PBNSTb15and PBNSTb20 for the corresponding concentrations of 0.1,0.5,1.0,1.5 and 2.0 mol% Tb^{3+} ions. Fig. 1 displays the polished image of the prepared PBNSTb glass samples at room temperature. The desired physical properties such as density, optical path (thickness), refractive index were measured and used for further investigation. These PBNSTb glasses XRD spectra were captured using RIGAKU X-ray diffractometer, and they covered the range of $10\text{--}80^\circ$. EDAX (oxford INCA FETX3). The measurement of the refractive index was made on an Abbe refractometer at 589.3 nm with 1-bromonaphthalene as a contact liquid. Using water as an immersion liquid, Archimedes' method was used to measure the density. The FT-IR investigations were carried out with BRUKER ALPHA-II FTIR spectrometer (2 cm^{-1} resolution). The UV-VIS-NIR spectrometer (model V-570, JASCO)which is used for recording optical absorption spectra, it has a wavelength resolutionof300–2000nm. The FLS-980 Fluorog-3 spectrometer was usedto record the photoluminescence spectra. Decay curves were measured by using a 980 nm pulsed laser diode to excite the samples and detected with an InGaAs detector and storage digital real-time oscilloscope (TDS 3012C, Tecktronix) with an accuracy of 0.01ms. Every experiment is carried out at room temperature.

Fig. 1. Fabricated PBNSTb glass samples.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Physical features

For the synthesized Tb³⁺: PBNS glasses, essential physical properties such as molar volume (V_m), concentration (N) of Tb³⁺ ions, dielectric constant (ε), molar refractivity (R_m) and reflection loss (R, %) etc., are measured as previously described [14-17]. The ratio of the volume occupied by a material to its amount, often provided at a specific temperature and pressure, is its molar volume (V_m). Molar volume (V_m) is the result of dividing the molar mass (M) by the density (d) and it is represented as

$$V_m(\text{cm}^3/\text{mol}) = \frac{M}{d} \quad (1)$$

where 'M' gives the effective molecular weight and 'd' is the density of the glass. A mole of a material's total polarizability is measured by its molar refraction (R_m). For isotropic substances like liquids, glasses, and cubic crystals, the relationship between R_m and molar volume (V_m) can be described as follows:

$$R_m(\text{cm}^3/\text{mol}) = \left(\frac{n^2-1}{n^2+1}\right) V_m \quad (2)$$

The reflection loss (R) provides the information about the reduction of intensity given by,

$$R(\%) = \left(\frac{n-1}{n+1}\right)^2 \times 100 \quad (3)$$

All the physical properties for the PBNSTb01, PBNSTb05, PBNSTb10, PBNSTb15 and PBNSTb20 glasses are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Physical properties of the PBNSTb glasses.

Physical parameters	0.1	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0
Density (ρ) (g/cm ³)	3.36	3.39	3.41	3.43	3.45
Thicknes (cm)	0.351	0.352	0.358	0.362	0.365
Refractive index (n)	1.651	1.651	1.650	1.638	1.631
Concentration (mol l ⁻¹)	0.011	0.058	0.117	0.175	0.233
Concentration (ions cm ⁻³ × 10 ²⁰)	1.409	7.058	1.410	2.115	2.813
	85.28	85.22	85.38	85.38	85.61

Molar volume, V_m (cm^3/mol)					
Molar Refractivity, R_m (cm^{-3})	31.13	31.11	31.13	30.68	30.49
Reflection losses, R (%)	6.03	6.03	6.01	5.84	5.75
Dielectric constant (ϵ)	2.725	2.725	2.722	2.683	2.66
Polar radius, r_p (A^0)	18.11	10.4	8.23	7.20	6.54
Electric polarizability ($\alpha_e \times 10^{-24}$)	12.32	12.31	12.32	12.14	12.07
Interionic distance, r_i (A^0)	44.96	25.8	20.44	17.87	16.24

3.2. XRD analysis

Fig. 2 shows the XRD spectrum of Tb^{3+} ion doped PBNSTb10 glass powder in the region of $10^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 80^\circ$. Because there is no distinct peak that correlates to any crystalline phase, it can be presumed that the sample illustrate the amorphous nature of the glass sample [18].

Fig. 2. XRD spectrum of PBNSTb10 glass sample powder.

3.3. EDAX and SEM analysis

Energy Dispersive X-ray Analysis (EDX), often known as EDS or EDAX, is an X-ray method for figuring out a material's composition. This study shows that Tb^{3+} ions are

successfully connected in the matrix. As seen in Fig. 3, this spectrum confirms that the O, Bi, P, Nd, Sr, and Tb ions are present in the existing glass systems. The combination of glass elements, together with their weights and atomic ratios, are shown in Table 2. The scanning electron micrograph (SEM) images of the un doped and Tb³⁺-doped PBNS glasses are shown in Fig. 4(a)-(f). These pictures demonstrate how the particles are not equally dispersed and have uneven shapes. The uneven temperature distribution throughout the synthesis process is the cause of the irregular shapes and sizes of SEM pictures. According to SEM data, the particles in the current study are compressed in size and dispersed randomly.

Fig. 3. EDAX spectrum of PBNSTb10 glass sample.

Fig.4. SEM images of (a) PBNS (b) PBNSTb01 (c) PBNSTb05 (d) PBNSTb10 (e)PBNSTb15 (f) PBNSTb20

Table 2. Elements weight and Atomic % of PBNSTb10 glass.

S. No	Element	Weight %	Atomic %
1	OK	32.49	66.46
2	NaK	1.85	2.64
3	SrL	5.42	2.02
4	PK	20.58	21.75
5	BiM	21.06	3.3
6	TbL	18.6	3.83

3.4. FTIR studies

The FTIR spectra of Terbium doped PBNS glasses were obtained at 4000–500 cm^{-1} as shown in Fig. 5, in order to gather the information for the structural and functional studies. The bands at 709 cm^{-1} and 900 cm^{-1} are due to symmetric stretching and bending vibrations of the halogen compound C-Bi group [18]. The bands at 1204 cm^{-1} corresponds to asymmetric stretching mode of the non-bridging oxygen atoms bonded to phosphorus atoms (P=O) [19,20]. The IR bands positioned around 1465–1651 cm^{-1} is associated with bending vibration of Bi-O group. The bands around 2950–3760 cm^{-1} are reveals the presence of O–H bonding or Hydrogen bonding vibrations of the glass matrix [21]. The PBNSTb glass system wave numbers and their related functional groups are shown Table 3.

Fig. 5. FTIR spectra of terbium doped PBNS glass samples.

Table 3. FTIR band position and band assignment of PBNSTb glasses.

S.No	Band position in (cm ⁻¹)	Band Assignment
1	709	The C–Bi stretching vibration of the halogen compound group.
2	900	Asymmetric stretching vibrations of P-O-P group
3	1204	Asymmetric stretching vibrational mode of the NBO atoms linked to phosphorus atoms (P=O)
4	1465	The bending vibration of Bi -O group
5	2859	Anti-asymmetric stretching vibration of the Water molecules
6	2960	O–H-Bonding
7	3382-3760	Hydrogen bonding vibration

3.5. Optical absorption studies

It is commonly recognized that the local structure of the ions in which they are incorporated (the bonding between RE and the ligand, the strength of the field, and the symmetry surrounding the RE ions) determines the optical characteristics of RE ions. To put it another way, the optical absorption and emission characteristics as well as the fluorescence decay features can be significantly impacted by the surrounding ligand field. Designing and developing glasses for laser and optical amplifier applications requires an understanding of these relationships between host glass structure and RE properties. Judd–Ofelt intensity parameters are crucial spectroscopic parameters of radiative processes of RE ions. They are sensitive to changes in the local environment and are phenomenological features of the host matrix's influence on the absorption and emission properties [22–24]. Previous studies have demonstrated that Tb³⁺ and Eu³⁺ are excellent indicator ions for local structure investigations near the RE ions due to their electronic structure [24,25]. In order to determine the local structure properties surrounding the

RE ions for specific applications, absorption, emission, and decay properties were derived for the Tb^{3+} -doped phosphate glasses in the current study.

The absorption spectrum of 1.0 mol% Tb_4O_7 -doped phosphate glass is displayed in Figure 6. The bands at 514 nm that correspond to the ${}^7F_6 \rightarrow {}^5D_4$ transitions of Tb^{3+} ions are visible in the absorption spectra. The absorption band at roughly 1680 nm was deconvoluted into three absorption bands using Gaussian distributions, which are attributable to the transitions from the ground state 7F_6 to the excited states ${}^7F_2, {}^7F_1, {}^7F_0$. The ${}^7F_6 \rightarrow {}^7F_3$ transition of the Tb^{3+} ion is the cause of the band at 1780 nm. Additionally, it was discovered that the spectrum resembles that of the other host matrices doped with Tb^{3+} [26, 27].

Fig. 6. Optical absorption spectra of PBNSTb10 glass in (a) VIS (b) NIR region.

3.6. Luminescence Spectra

Fig. 7 demonstrates the excitation and emission spectra of PBNSTb1.0 glass. The excitation spectrum was captured by observing the terbium ${}^5D_4 \rightarrow {}^7F_5$ emission at 542 nm. The spectrum displays eight bands which are associated with transitions from the 7F_6 ground state to the different excited states ${}^5H_4, {}^5H_6, {}^5H_7, {}^5L_7, {}^5L_9, {}^5G_5, {}^5G_6,$ and 5D_3 located at 284, 303, 318, 342, 351, 358, 368 and 377 nm, wavelengths respectively [28,29]. The most noticeable of these transitions, ${}^7F_6 \rightarrow {}^5D_3$ confirms the strong absorption at 377 nm, demonstrating that the current glass system may be efficiently activated by a UV excitation source [30]. Consequently, the PL spectra for the prepared glasses have been noted under 377 nm excitation as shown in Fig. 8. The PL spectra manifest four emission bands initiated from excited level 5D_4 to lower levels ${}^7F_{6,5,4,3}$

which gives emission at 488, 542, 583, and 619 nm respectively [31]. In general, the emission of Tb^{3+} falls in blue and green-red region originated from 5D_3 and 5D_4 levels radiatively, being populated from 5D_2 level by non-radiative relaxation. In this instance, emissions from 5D_4 level have been identified since the energy difference in 5D_3 and 5D_4 level is small (6000 cm^{-1}). 5D_4 level has been efficiently populated by non-radiative relaxation from upper excited levels and therefore the spectrum exhibits emission lines from 5D_4 level only [32, 33]. According to emission spectra, the green emission, which is appropriate for use in laser and other display applications, is most noticeable around 542 nm [32]. In the present investigation, the intensity of $^5D_4 \rightarrow ^7F_5$ transition increases with increase of Tb^{3+} concentration from 0.5 to 2 mol %, showing the absence of luminescence quenching phenomenon. This may be due to the wide energy gap ($\sim 14,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and lack of cross-relaxation channels. Therefore, it can be inferred that increasing the concentration of Tb^{3+} ions in PBNS glasses will further increase the luminescence's intensity. Fig. 9 displays the energy level diagram for Tb^{3+} ions in PBNS glass, which is based on the energies of several transitions derived from the absorption, excitation, and emission spectra. From the energy level diagram, it is noted that the energy gap between the 5D_3 and 5D_4 levels is equal to the energy difference within the 7F_J ($J = 0-6$) multiplets. As seen in Fig. 9, the energy level diagram also displays distinct emission transitions seen from the 5D_4 and 5D_3 states.

Fig.7. (a) Excitation (monitored at 542 nm) and emission spectrum (excited at 377 nm) of PBNSTb10 glass sample.

Fig. 8. Emission spectra of phosphate glasses doped with different Tb^{3+} concentrations.

Fig. 9. Partial energy level diagram of Tb^{3+} ion in phosphate glasses.

.7. Decay lifetime:

In order to measure the lifetimes of 5D_4 state, decay curves are recorded for all the concentrations of Tb^{3+} :PBNS glasses. The decay curves for the 5D_4 level for various Tb^{3+} ion concentrations are displayed in Fig.10. These curves were generated by tracking the green emission at 542 nm that is attributable to the $^5D_4 \rightarrow ^7F_5$ transition. It is clear that decay curves in the glasses under investigation have a single exponential character at any concentration. The experimental lifetimes for 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0 % of Tb^{3+} ions are found to be 2.79, 2.63, 2.62, 2.6 and 2.59 ms, respectively, which are presented in Table 4 and these values compared with other reported glasses [34-36]. The lifetime for the 5D_4 level was found to be higher than fluoroborate [34] and tellurite [35] glasses and more or less similar to fluorophosphate [36] glasses. It has been found that the lifetime of the 5D_4 level barely decreases when the Tb^{3+} concentration increases. This implies that energy migration has no impact on the 5D_4 lifetime, in contrast to most Tb^{3+} -doped glasses. [37-40]. The high energy gap ($\sim 15000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) below the 5D_4 level is also expected to make the multiphonon emission rate insignificant. Because of the longer fluorescence lifetime of Tb^{3+} ions in these glasses, the pump threshold can be lowered to get the visible laser output.

Fig. 10. Decay curves for the 5D_4 level of Tb^{3+} ion in PBNSTb glasses.

Table 4. Concentration (N, mol %) and experimental lifetimes(τ_{exp} , ms) for $^5D_4 \rightarrow ^7F_5$ transitions of Tb^{3+} ion phosphate glasses along with reported glasses.

(mol.%)	N Phosphate [Present work]	Fluoroborate [1]	Tellurite [2]	Fluorophosphate [3]
0.1	2.79	1.89	0.30	2.65
0.5	2.63	1.68	0.26	2.91
1.0	2.62	1.39	0.21	2.93
	2.60	1.30	-	-
2.0	2.59	1.12	0.16	2.94

3.8. Chromaticity coordinates

To investigate the color emitted by Tb^{3+} -doped PBNS glasses under 377 nm illumination, the coordinates of chromaticity were determined from the luminescence spectra using the Commission Internationale de l'Eclairage (CIE 1931) system [41]. Based on the tri-stimulus values for X, Y, and Z the chromaticity coordinates for x, y, and z are obtained using the following formulas:

$$x = \frac{X}{X+Y+Z} \quad (1)$$

$$y = \frac{Y}{X+Y+Z} \quad (2)$$

$$z = \frac{Z}{X+Y+Z} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 11 gives the location of assessed chromaticity coordinates (x, y) of (0.325, 0.548), (0.337, 0.581), (0.34, 0.592), (0.338, 0.594) and (0.34, 0.596) for PBNSTb01, PBNSTb05, PBNSTb10, PBNSTb15 and PBNSTb20 glasses, respectively. In particular, all-glass samples show green light emission (542 nm) as a result, the CIE coordinates which the mostly lie in shade of lime-green region. The color coordinates and colour purity (CP) for the studied

glasses are presented in Table 5. These chromaticity coordinates are close to BSGdCaTb01 (0.311, 0.597) [42], ZnAl₂O₄: Tb (0.340, 0.560) [43] and LATB (0.30, 0.58) [44]. Correlated color temperature (CCT), which shows the temperature of a Planckian blackbody radiator closest to the operational point in the chromaticity diagram, can also be used to assess the quality of the light that is released [45]. The CCT values are calculated using the color coordinates by the McCamy empirical formula of Eq. (1.33) [46]. Table 5 displays the CCT values acquired for the current Tb³⁺-doped glasses. When CCT levels exceed 5000 K, they reveal cold white light that is useful for household appliances, when CCT values fall below 5000 K, they indicate warm light that is useful for industrial lighting applications [47].

Fig. 11. The CIE-1931 chromaticity diagram of PBNSTb glasses

Table 5. The CIE coordinates, and Colour purity (CP) values of the samples with varying doping concentrations.

C(Tb ³⁺)	CIE (x, y)	CCT	CP
0.5	(0.325, 0.548)	5647	54
0.1	(0.337, 0.581)	5428	61

1.0	(0.340, 0.592)	5380	64
1.5	(0.338, 0.594)	5414	65
2.0	(0.340, 0.596)	5389	64

. Conclusion

The traditional melt quenching method was used to successfully generate Tb³⁺-doped phosphate glasses for varying dopant concentrations. For the Tb³⁺-doped phosphate glasses, concentration-dependent photoluminescence and lifetime were investigated. The strongest peak, which is used as the excitation energy for luminescence research, is seen in both the excitation and absorption spectra at 377 nm. Intense green emission ascribed to ⁵D₄→⁷F₅ transitions, respectively, have been observed from the luminescence spectra. For the ⁵D₄→⁷F₅ transition, no quenching in light intensity has been seen. The decay curves for the ⁵D₄ level of Tb³⁺ ion follow a single-exponential decay for all the concentrations with a small lifetime fluctuation from 2.79 to 2.59 ms. The longer lifetime of the ⁵D₄ level could decrease the pump threshold to get visible laser emission. The results suggest that the present phosphate glasses could be useful as a visible green laser media at 542 nm.

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